

Interaction of Amino Acids with Potassium Hexacyanochromate(III)

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In alkaline solutions, cyano groups of potassium hexacyanochromate(III) are replaced by amino acids on irradiation with ultraviolet light. Prolonged irradiation results in the precipitation of $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$. The complexes: $[(\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_4(\text{amino acid}))^{-2}]$ and $[(\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_2(\text{amino acid})_2)^{-1}]$ have been separated by thin layer chromatography and characterised by chemical analysis and infrared spectra. Ultraviolet and visible spectra of the complexes has also been discussed.

THE hexacyanochromate(III) anion is indefinitely stable in neutral or basic solutions, while it undergoes rapid aquation in acidic solutions. In aqueous solutions, $[\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_6]^{-3}$ on irradiation with ultraviolet light undergoes aquation^{1,2} with the release of CN^- ions. Since it has been conclusively shown that cyano groups are replaced by H_2O on irradiation with ultraviolet light, it was thought worthwhile to attempt the replacement of cyano groups by other suitable ligands on irradiating their aqueous solutions with ultraviolet light. In this communication we report our results on the photochemical interaction of $\text{K}_3\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_6$ with glycine, histidine and aspartic acid.

Experimental

$\text{K}_3\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_6$ was prepared by the method given in 'Inorganic Synthesis', 1946, Vol. 2, p. 203, from AR grade reagents. Glycine, histidine and aspartic acid in their hydrochloride form were BDH products and their solutions were prepared in double distilled water.

Mixtures of $\text{K}_3\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_6$ and the amino acids were exposed to ultraviolet light with an ultraviolet lamp (Wotan Ultravital Ux, Gur 53~, 220-230 V, 300 W mnX, Made in Germany).

Spectrophotometric studies were carried out with Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer. Infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded in the KBr phase by the thin film technique on Beckman IR 20 spectrophotometer.

For chemical analysis, Cr(III) was estimated colorimetrically using diphenylcarbazide³ after decomposing the isolated complexes by boiling with conc. HCl, while nitrogen, carbon and hydrogen estimations were carried out at microanalytical laboratories, Chemistry Department, IIT, Kanpur.

Isolation of the complexes

Solutions of $\text{K}_3\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_6$ and amino acids mixed in the ratio of 1 : 2 were exposed to ultraviolet light for 5 hr. After adding thrice the volume of absolute alcohol along with a few drops of acetone, the solutions were shaken vigorously and allowed to stand for a few hours. The oily liquid was decanted off and washed several times with alcohol. The oily liquid was applied on the edge of a glass plate coated with a uniform layer of chromatographic grade silica. The oily liquid was then eluted with a mixture of butanol, water and glacial acetic acid (ratio 6 : 1 : 1) for about 5 hr. Two distinct layers separated out which were scooped out with a spatula and the complex extracted with water. The solution was filtered and evaporated to dryness on a water bath. The residue was finely powdered and kept in vacuum over CaCl_2 for 24 hr.

Results and Discussions

When aqueous mixtures of $\text{K}_3\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_6$ and the amino acids are irradiated with ultraviolet light, the colour changes from yellow to light red, pink and deep red for glycine, histidine and aspartic acid respectively with an increase of pH from around 8.0 to 9.0. The observed colour changes indicate the formation of new complexes while the increase in pH is indicative of release of CN^- ions and subsequent substitution of cyano groups by the amino acid molecules. Prolonged irradiation results in the precipitation of $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$.

The irradiated solution was analysed by paper chromatography using butanol, water and glacial acetic acid mixture (ratio 6 : 1 : 1) for elution. It was found that two distinct spots were obtained after elution for 5 hr, which shows that two substituted

species are formed during the reaction. Chemical analysis of the components isolated by thin layer chromatography shows the products to be :

TABLE I—CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF THE AMINO ACID SUBSTITUTED COMPLEXES

Complexes	%Cr	%C	%H	%N
$\text{K}_2[\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_4(\text{glycine})]$				
calcd.	16.91	23.37	1.29	22.72
found	16.73	23.11	1.10	22.86
$\text{K}[\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_2(\text{glycine})_2]$				
calcd.	17.85	24.74	2.76	19.23
found	17.69	24.80	2.68	19.25
$\text{K}_2[\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_4(\text{histidine})]$				
calcd.	13.40	30.95	2.06	25.25
found	13.51	30.76	2.19	25.07
$\text{K}[\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_2(\text{histidine})_2]$				
calcd.	11.52	37.24	3.57	24.87
found	11.47	37.31	3.51	24.90
$\text{K}_2[\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_4(\text{aspartic acid})]$				
calcd.	14.20	26.25	1.65	19.12
found	14.34	26.38	1.43	19.36
$\text{K}[\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_2(\text{aspartic acid})_2]$				
calcd.	16.92	39.07	3.93	11.72
found	16.80	38.99	3.97	11.63

The infrared spectral data of the isolated complexes, $\text{K}_3\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_6$ and the amino acids are tabulated in Table 2. The strong absorption bands in the region 3390–3450 cm^{-1} have been observed in all the complexes and may be assigned to the coupling of anti-symmetric and symmetric NH_2 stretching modes. Since the amino acids and their hydrochlorides do not show any absorption in the normal NH stretching region (3500–3300 cm^{-1}) but show a band in the 3130–3030 cm^{-1} region due to NH_3^+ stretching, the appearance of a band in the 3390–3450 cm^{-1} region suggests coordination of the amino acid to the metal through nitrogen of the amino groups⁴.

The strong absorption band in the 1600–1640 cm^{-1} region may be assigned to the antisymmetric stretching^{4,5} of the coordinated carboxylic group.

The characteristic $\text{C} \equiv \text{N}$ stretching frequency appears in the 2100 cm^{-1} region while it is observed at 2130 cm^{-1} in $\text{K}_3\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_6$. The $(\text{Cr}-\text{C} \equiv \text{N})$ absorption is in the 640–610 cm^{-1} region which appears at 660 cm^{-1} in $\text{K}_3\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_6$. In addition the complexes show absorption at 500 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to the Cr-N band and is absent in the spectra of $\text{K}_3\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_6$ as well as the amino acids. Thus chromium appears to be bound to the amino acid through nitrogen of the amino group and oxygen of the carboxylic group and the CN^- group. The following tentative structures may thus be assigned to the complexes :

AND

The ultraviolet and visible spectral characteristics of the amino acid substituted complexes are given in Table 3. The ultraviolet and visible spectra of $\text{K}_3\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_6$ shows two low intensity bands at 378 nm and 307 nm, which are assigned¹ to ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}$ and ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}$ transitions respectively. The high intensity charge transfer band at 260 nm is assigned to the $t_{2g} \rightarrow \pi^*$ MLCT transition^{1,10,11}. In the amino acid substituted complexes, the bands in the vicinity of 260 nm are also assigned to the $t_{2g} \rightarrow \pi^*$ MLCT transition.

In the case of symmetries lower than O_h , the octahedral states split¹² and thus the corresponding bands also split. In a tetragonal field, the cubic ground state ${}^4\text{A}_{2g}$ transforms into ${}^4\text{B}_1$, and the ${}^4\text{T}_{2g}$ level splits into ${}^4\text{B}_2$ and ${}^4\text{E}$ components. The ${}^4\text{B}_2$ component remains at the same energy (10 Dq) above the ground state but the ${}^4\text{E}$ level can be either above or below the ${}^4\text{B}_2$ level. The low intensity transitions around 380 nm and 310 nm are, therefore, assigned to the transitions ${}^4\text{B}_1 \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_1$, ${}^4\text{E}$ and ${}^4\text{B}_1 \rightarrow {}^4\text{E}$ respectively. The decreasing symmetry in mixed ligand complexes causes the removal of the σ -antibonding orbital degeneracy and thus, it precludes the ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}$ transition around 370 nm.

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA OF THE AMINO ACIDS, POTASSIUM HEXACYANOCROMATE(III) AND THE AMINO ACID SUBSTITUTED COMPLEXES

Complex	Absorption band at cm ⁻¹													
	3500—3400 BSt	3100	2960	2780	2580	2130 SSt	1620—1600 BM	1495	1440	1435	1400	1320	1275	660 SSt
Glycine		3100 SM	2960 SM	2780 SW	2580 BM	—	1600 SSt	1590 SM	1440 SM	1435 SM	1400 SSt	1320 SM	1275 Sh	600 SM
K ₂ [Cr(CN) ₄ (gly)]	3400 SM	3390 SM	3240 SM	2560 BW	2108 SSt	1160 SW	1125 SM	1040 SM	925 SSt	880 SSt	680 SSt	600 SM	560 SM	600 SM
K ₂ [Cr(CN) ₂ (gly) ₂]	3400 SM	3390 SM	3240 SM	2570 BW	2108 SSt	1120 SW	1080 SM	1015 SSt	960 SSt	880 Sh	680 SM	645 SSt	610 SW	550 SW
Histidine		3120 SM	2980 BM	2860 SM	2700 SM	—	1645 SSt	1600 SM	1570 SM	1500 Sh	1460 SSt	1420 SSt	1340 SSt	645 SSt
K ₂ [Cr(CN) ₄ (hist.)]	3435 SM	3400 SM				2100 SSt	1640 Sh	1635 SSt	1500 Sh	1460 SSt	1460 SSt	1340 SM	1160 SW	630 SSt
K ₂ [Cr(CN) ₂ (hist.) ₂]	3440 SM	3400 SM				2105 SSt	1640 Sh	1635 SSt	1500 Sh	1465 SSt	1465 SSt	1340 SM	1160 SW	630 SSt
Aspartic acid		3110 SM	2990 BM	2780 SW	2560 SW	—	1635 SSt	1595 SSt	1560 SSt	1460 SSt	1400 SSt	1340 SM	1160 SW	630 SSt
K ₂ [Cr(CN) ₄ (aspt)]	3450 SM	3400 SM				2100 SSt	1625 SSt	1460 SSt	1400 SSt	1340 SM	1340 SM	1160 SW	1100 SSt	635 SM
K ₂ [Cr(CN) ₂ (aspt) ₂]	3450 SM	3400 SM				2100 SSt	1625 SSt	1460 SSt	1400 SSt	1330 SM	1330 SM	1160 SW	1100 SSt	635 SM

St = strong; S = sharp; M = medium; W = weak; B = broad; Sh = shoulder.

TABLE 3—ULTRAVIOLET AND VISIBLE SPECTRAL DATA FOR THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Absorption band at nm	Assignment
K ₃ [Cr(CN) ₆]*	337	⁴ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{2g}
	307	→ ⁴ T _{1g}
	260	t _{2g} → MLCT
K[Cr(CN) ₂ (glycine) ₂]	510	⁴ B ₁ → ⁴ E
	410	→ ⁴ A ₂ , ⁴ E
	255	t _{2g} → MLCT
K[Cr(CN) ₂ (histidine) ₂]	510	⁴ B ₁ → ⁴ E
	370	→ ⁴ A ₂ , ⁴ E
	270	t _{2g} → MLCT
K[Cr(CN) ₂ (aspartic acid) ₂]	525	⁴ B ₁ → ⁴ B
	380	→ ⁴ A ₂ , ⁴ E
	265	t _{2g} → MLCT

* Data reported vide Ref. 1.

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